

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Using exceptions for control-flow\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to code that forces developers to handle exceptions for control-flow. Exception handling itself does not represent a code smell, but this should not be the only alternative available to developers to handle an error in client code. When developers have no freedom to decide if an error is exceptional or not, this is considered a code smell. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): To prevent a library function from always forcing third-party code to handle an error as an exception, we can initially rename the original function, adding a trailing ! at the end of its name. In Elixir, there is a convention where a ! (i.e., *trailing* or *bang*) at the end of a function name indicates that it may raise an exception.
 2. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): After renaming the original function by adding a ! at the end of its name, we can use this refactoring to duplicate the renamed original function. This copy should have the original function's name, without the ! at the end. Instead of raising exceptions, it should return data in the *tuple* format (i.e., `{:ok, ...}` or `{:error, msg}`). The message provided in the error *tuple* should be the same as the one originally displayed in the exception version.
 3. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): Finally, we can use the present refactoring to change the *bang* variant (i.e., the original function that raises an exception, with ! at the end of its name). With this transformation, the raising version is implemented on top of the non-raising version of the code.
-
1. [\[Introduce processes\]](#): Another possibility for removing this smell is, if the module where the function that raises an exception is not a process (e.g., *GenServer* or *Task*), we can use this refactoring to transform the module into a process.
 2. [\[Moving error-handling mechanisms to supervision trees\]](#): When a process is using defensive programming (i.e., `try..rescue`) to handle exceptions and even control the execution flow, we can use this refactoring to eliminate this type of handling, transitioning instead to the "Let it crash" style.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Accessing non-existent map/struct fields\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when *struct* or *map* fields are accessed dynamically, which may result in *nil* values that can be ambiguous and lead developers to introduce bugs. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Default value for an absent key in a Map\]](#): When trying to access the value of a key from a *Map* dynamically, it is not possible to determine if a key is non-existent or if it has an associated *nil* value. This refactoring can eliminate the smell, as the ambiguity in the returns of dynamic accesses will no longer occur after its application.
 - [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): If the smell instance occurs in the function signature, such as in a guard clause, we can use this refactoring to extract the value of that field and then use it in the guard. This way, we can clearly determine if a field does not exist or if it simply has an associated *nil* value.
 - [\[Simplifying checks by using truthness condition\]](#): Optionally, when using dynamic access to fields of a *Map* and needing to return a default value for non-existent fields or those associated with *nil*, we can perform this refactoring to solve this issue, thus producing cleaner code.
 - [\[Explicit a double boolean negation\]](#): Optionally, if we are using double boolean negation to check if a dynamically accessed field in a *Map* exists, this refactoring can improve code readability by replacing the unintuitive logic with helper functions that utilize pattern matching.
1. [\[Struct field access elimination\]](#): Optionally, if accesses to the same field, whether it exists or not, occur many times within a function, we can use this refactoring to replace these accesses with a temporary variable responsible for storing the value of that field.
 2. [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, when a temporary variable extracted from a *struct* field is only used in an equality comparison in a guard, extracting and using that variable is unnecessary, as we can perform that equality comparison directly with pattern matching. To do this, we can use this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Inappropriate intimacy\]](#) smell? *

In Elixir, this code smell can be felt in *impure functions*. These functions can access internal values of other modules that are not received via parameters, generating excessive coupling. Particularly, the values accessed by impure functions of a module "A", can be internal details of a module "B", obtained by calling functions of module "B", inside functions of module "A". To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Closure conversion\]](#): A specific type of Inappropriate intimacy can be seen in closures, which are impure anonymous functions, as they access variables outside their scope. One way to remove this smell is by transforming the closure into a pure anonymous function.
 2. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): Imagine the scenario where an anonymous function *A* is defined within a named function *B*. Furthermore, consider that *A* accesses a variable in its body that is a parameter of *B*, which is not passed as a parameter to *A* (i.e., function *A* is a closure). When applying the previous refactoring to remove the Inappropriate intimacy instance in *A*, we may end up with unused parameters in the named function *B*. Therefore, we can use the present refactoring in *B* to fix it.
- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): If a function in module *A* is impure because it accesses internal details of module *B* without receiving them through its parameters, we can remove this smell by moving the function from *A* to *B*, thus reducing the coupling between modules.
1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): If the modules involved in an instance of this smell have common interests, we can use this refactoring to put their commonality in a new module and make them high-cohesive and low-coupling modules.
 2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Compile-time global configuration\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function uses module attributes for configuration purposes, thereby preventing run-time configuration. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract constant\]](#): To remove this smell caused by using *Application Environment* in compile-time to define module's attributes (i.e., constants), we can perform this refactoring in reverse, that is, perform an *inline* operation.
 - [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): We can also use this refactoring to create a copy of the compile-time defined constant and replace its definition with a call to *Application.compile_env/3* instead of *Application.fetch_env!/2*.
1. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): Another possibility would be to replace the location where a compile-time defined constant is used with a call to the *Application Environment* function responsible for defining the constant's content. This can be done using this refactoring.
 2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): Finally, if the compile-time defined constant is no longer used in the module, we can simply remove it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Comments\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function is documented using explanatory comments instead of *@doc*, or when comments are used to compensate for poorly written code. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract function\]](#): If a comment explains a block of code, that block can be extracted into a separate function. The name of the new function can often be derived from the comment itself.
- [\[Extract expressions\]](#): If a comment is intended to explain a complex expression, the expression should be split into understandable sub-expressions using this refactoring.
- [\[Extract constant\]](#): If a comment is used to explain magic numbers, this refactoring can replace the comments with constants that have human-friendly names.
- [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): If a function, expression, or constant has already been extracted, but comments are still necessary to explain what they do, give a self-explanatory name to them using this operation.
- [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): If a comment is used to document the types of a function's parameters or the type of its return value, that comment can be replaced by a function specification using the *@spec* module attribute.
- [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): Alternatively, if a comment is used to document data structures received as parameters of a function or even returned by a function, this comment can be replaced by a type specification using the *@type* and *@typedoc* module attributes.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Using App Configuration for libraries\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a library function is configured using parameterization mechanisms instead of arguments, thereby limiting its reuse by clients. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): When we have a library function that depends on globally defined values, which reduces its reusability, we can use this refactoring to add a new optional parameter of type *Keyword list* with a default value. This new parameter allows the function to be configured in different ways when called. If the optional parameter is not provided in the call, the function will continue to behave as originally, using the same global configurations.
2. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): We can also use this refactoring to explicitly document the type of the added parameter (i.e., *Keyword list*).

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Complex branching\]](#) smell? *

When a function assumes the responsibility of handling multiple errors alone, it can increase its cyclomatic complexity (metric of control-flow) and become incomprehensible. This situation can configure a specific instance of "Long function", a traditional code smell, but has implications of its own. Under these circumstances, this function could get very confusing, difficult to maintain and test, and therefore bug-proneness. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract function\]](#): When a function uses a conditional statement with many different branches, each responsible for handling a specific error type, we can use this refactoring to delegate each branch (i.e., handling of a response type) to a different new private function. This approach makes the code cleaner, more concise, and readable.
- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): Another possibility is to use this refactoring to break down complex branching into a multi-clause function, where each clause handles a different error type. This approach enhances readability and maintainability by organizing the code according to distinct error scenarios.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

[Enviar](#)

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